

The making of slums: An analysis of Indian parliamentary debates, 1953–2014.

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Slums are a highly debated topic with an ever-shifting political position. These political positions address to intervene and eradicate slums, although research has for decades shown that slum is a mere symptom of inequity and not its cause. This article investigates the rationality and discourse which legitimizes state actions and uncovers how slums are discursively produced. It does so by analysing the debates from the question hour of the upper house of the Indian parliament from 1953 until 2014 and complements it through the analysis of slum-related policies and legislation. The article outlines the historical progression of slum conceptualizations, the rationale around it, and how this rationality reigns policy and legislation debates. The article demonstrates how, over a period of 61 years, the slums were created in the parliament and how they have been transformed from a political subject into a technical object. The article concludes with calls for a greater engagement with discourses and rationalities to counter state's disenfranchising slum policies and the shrinking political space.

Keywords: slums; governmentality; parliamentary debates; calculation; problematization; knowledge production.

INTRODUCTION

In 1957, during a *Rajya Sabha* (Indian Parliament's upper house) debate one parliamentarian posed the following question: 'What is the definition of

a slum, and which areas are declared slum areas?' (Chand, 1957, p. 2690). The debate transcripts do not reveal whether this was a genuine enquiry to better understand the issue or a pointed critique via a rhetorical question. Regardless, the Chairman (Speaker), instead letting the minister reply, mocked the question by asking back: 'What is the definition of a slum? Physical or mental slum?' (Chand, 1957, p. 2690). Contrastingly, by the early 2010s, there were multiple slum definitions resulting in data mismatches. Replying to one such question, the minister stated that:

‘... the Government is aware that the Census Office and the National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO) have come up with different estimates of India’s slum population ... The NSSO has covered only *two types* of slums i.e. Notified and Non-notified while Census has considered *three types* of slums, viz. Notified, Recognized, and Identified’ (R P N Singh [Minister of State in The Ministry of Home Affairs], Indian National Congress (INC)] cited Irani, 2014, p. 17) (emphasis added).

These excerpts show a shifting and overlapping slum conception. Tracing these discourses and the underlying knowledge production, could help us better understand the knowledge formations that aid the normalization of urban inequality (van Gent & Jaffe, 2017). Such an investigation can illustrate the strategies that can be employed to counter and contest the hegemonic discourses underlying knowledge production mechanisms about our cities.

Slums have been the focus of international action for marginalized population’s betterment. By contrast, Perlman's (1979) work has shown that slums (or favelas) are the symptoms of larger socio-economic disparities and

that action on the slum itself will not yield any results if not accompanied by measures to reduce inequality. Nonetheless, the fascination with improving the slums or with building cities without slums continues, both as a political slogan and as a policy paradigm around the globe. The State's misplaced slum action been discussed by various authors (Arabindoo, 2011; Ghertner, 2015); however, there is a gap in understanding the causality of such actions and how knowledge for such actions are produced and framed. Therefore, the first question that this article engages with is, why States focus on slum improvement while it has been well known that this cannot be the remedy to socio-economic inequality. Over the years, the State has devised means to measure, categorize, and map slums, transforming it into a legal entity. The way slums are being defined and therefore the way they are understood has been changing. This discursive nature has impacts on the way slums are treated and environment is engaged with (Sharan, 2014). Other researchers have argued that to intervene, in a society or in the urbanization process, the State needs to count and produce knowledge regarding the governable subjects (Ghertner, 2015; Legg, 2006; Scott, 1998). It is thus eminent to enquire how these categorizations and definitions come into being and how they change. Therefore, the second question that this article engages with is, how slums are made into conceivable subject by the State. Consequently, I intend to broaden the literature on discursive production of slums, from the analysis of mere misplaced State actions, to a historicized genealogy of rationalities. I do this with using the parliamentary debates where the

tandem between the executive and the legislature produce governance discourses.

Urban development and thus the issue of slums are the State Governments' prerogative in India. However, the Central Government has been interfering from the beginning of independent India in urban development and slum issues through advice, directives and funding schemes, and model legislations. I outline the making of slums by these 'interferences' of the central government using the *Rajya Sabha* debates.

The parliament begins with the question hour when the members ask questions to the ministers. Typically, these questions are independent of the legislations being discussed and they therefore present a diverse set of issues. Such debates from the question hour since 1953 (the first session) until 2014 (the last session of the recently completed government) form the article's main archive. It consists of a total of 1228 debates (main questions and supplements) which were identified by searching for the words 'slum', '*basti*', '*JJ*' (varying combinations), and 'informal' in their content (henceforth *Rajya Sabha* debates). To understand these debates in their wider context, policy documents – (i) The slum area (improvement & clearance) bill 1956, (ii) National Housing Policy 1988 (including revisions of 1994, 1998 and 2007), (iii) Rajiv Awas Yojana 2009 – and all the 12 five-year plans have also been analysed. The datasets were qualitatively analysed by manually coding the documents and the groundedness of these codes are used for quantitative insights.

I discuss the results in the following four section in a chronological order. These sections highlight the four kinds of discourse and should not necessarily be understood as stages.

THE ERA OF EPIDEMIOLOGY: FROM EARLY-1950s UNTIL LATE-1960s

The partition of India in 1947, moved a large number of people from West Pakistan to Delhi who settled into the Old Delhi *katras*. *Katras* are compact private neighbourhoods developed during the Mughal era. Due to a high residential demand from post-partition migrants, the *katra* owners divided the already compact buildings into multiple tenements. Resource-constrained migrants came to live in these high-density neighbourhoods that lacked civic amenities¹.

Delhi at the time was administered directly by the Central Government, which encouraged the *Rajya Sabha* to discuss the issues of Old Delhi *katras*, which were often referred to as slums. Two related concerns were expressed in the *Rajya Sabha*: (i) the lacking civic amenities, mostly ascribed to increasing population density and deteriorating building conditions; and (ii) the negative impact of these conditions on the citizens. Deficient amenities and neighbourhood congestion due to high density were taken as the major slum-defining factors. By contrast, other causes for the development of ‘slum-like’ conditions, such as migration induced by religious

¹ Old Delhi densification did not result from partition-led migration alone. Both density and deterioration of amenities had been a concern in British India. C.f. (Legg, 2007; Sharan, 2014).

and caste violence, poverty, and exclusionary planning (both economic and spatial), were largely ignored in the debates. This framing took myriad urban issues of a newly formed nation and subsumed it within the narrow discussions on slums. Furthermore, this framing reduced the issue of slums to their physical aspects (lack of civic amenities, overcrowding) and thus associated the slum to a circumscribed endemic physical space.

Government's control over these areas was limited because most *katras* were on private land. In 1956, the Central Government introduced the Slum Areas (Improvement & Clearance) Act (henceforth the 1956 act) that gave the government power to notify a particular area as a slum. Once notified, the government was legally entitled to intervene. During the presentation of this bill, the minister summarized previous slum preoccupations as:

The city of Delhi is now overcrowded, and in certain areas the conditions are extremely detrimental, not only to health and morals, but also to the safety of the people living in those areas. The buildings are of a ramshackle character, dilapidated and hardly fit for human habitation. There are no amenities of any type, neither drinking water, nor light, nor roads, nor drains. So, they are an eyesore. And what is much worse, they are dangerous to the very safety, health and morals of the people, not only those who live there, but also those who occupy houses in the neighbourhood. (Govind Ballabh Pant [Home Minister, INC] cited in Ballabh Pant, 1956, p. 2974)

The slum was theorized as an epidemic to be contained, a view that can be found from the early 1950s until the late 1960s in the *Rajya Sabha* debates. Thus, the myriad urban issues and the political predicament of

dealing with them, got subsumed into slum discussions and further got transformed into a legal concern.

During this era, the term 'slum area' was most frequently used. The connotation was that slum areas, like contaminated areas, need special treatment. By framing slums as a public health issue, leading from Legg's (2006) argument of how calculations are envisaged and presented, the State legitimized and delineated its action via slum demolitions without any consultation or participation of the residents. The 1956 act represents the first step of the State to provide itself with the instruments for acting on slums, as they could now be demarcated and notified. This also led to a questioning of the above-mentioned self-evident nature of slums: Because in the 1956 act, there was no definitive slum definition but open to interpretation indicators. Consequently, parliamentarians increasingly contested the demarcation of certain areas as a slum. What started as clear understanding of the problem (the slum) and the precise solution (slum demolition) started to become contested and politicized after the 1956 act.

It should, however, be noted that any focused attempt to define slums was regularly avoided, as shown with the example in the introduction. These debates present an interesting paradox: while there seems to be a consensus on the conceptualization of slums as infected areas, it proved difficult to concretely delimit slums in a physical space, as opposed to the intent of the 1956 act. The idea of infected areas was so embedded that the various issues raised were subsumed within the all-encompassing action of slum clearance, e.g.:

Dalpat Singh [Other]: ... what special arrangement the Government is making in the matter of drinking water and medical facilities, in view of the unhealthy localities in the various cities? ...

B. S. Murthy [Minister of State in The Ministry of Health and Family Planning and The Ministry of Works, Housing and Urban Development, INC]: Sir, once the slums are cleared, the insanitary conditions will *automatically* disappear and water supply and other facilities will be provided. (Kant, 1970, p. 3) (emphasis added)

The problem of slums is often referred to as an 'eyesore', which the then Home Minister also uses in the first quote of this section. Envisaging the slum and its presentation is also related to larger concerns of image consciousness and development. In 1970, drawing attention to the media coverage, a parliamentarian emphasized:

A. D. Mani [INC]: May I ask the Minister whether his attention has been drawn to the description in the foreign press that Calcutta is the biggest slum in the world, and it is a disgrace to us. (Kant, 1970, p. 3)

These considerations resurge during the early 2000s in the judiciary debates (Ramanathan, 2006). Ghertner (2015) have discussed this phenomenon in the context of Delhi, where citizenship rights of slum dwellers have been suspended in the court of law using the aesthetic argument, making slums worthy of demolitions.

Further, the debates drew from the deficiencies of sanitation-related infrastructure in a neighbourhood to recognize it as a slum. There were multiple debates that point to infrastructure deficiencies as a slum identifier, which is intertwined with the politics of visibility. For example, in a debate titled 'Slum clearance in New Delhi', the question was framed

using the phrase 'dirt and squalor' instead of the term 'slum'. Even the then Health Minister replied with the same framing (Dhage, 1957).

The portrayal of slums as illegitimate and therefore illegal was also articulated in this era. The settlements may not be illegal, but the discourse renders them so. In a 1960 debate, for example, Naik [INC] points to slum growth by stating: 'While the aim of the Government is to clear the city of slum conditions, why is it that the Government were not vigilant before these unauthorized constructions came into being?' (Naik, 1960, p. 2570). Such framings does not directly label the slum as illegal, but implicitly constructs such an understanding by linking slum growth to lack of vigilance by the government.

The slum was initially understood as a self-evident concept in this era. Hence, the 1956 act had no definitive slum-definition, but it opened up vigorous contestations on defining the idea of slums in the legislature. These debates also led to the construction of a slum subject albeit not precise.

SLUMS AS NECESSARY BUT IMPROVABLE EVIL: FROM EARLY-1970s UNTIL MID-1980s

In the 1950s and 1960s, the government was attempting to demolish and rebuild 'all' the slums. To resettle the relocated slum dwellers, land needed to be acquired and developed. In the early 1960s, the government decided to massively buy land to facilitate planning (Dhage, 1960), which was later termed 'socializing land' (Menon et al., 1972, p. 12).

While the slum clearance programmes continued, various problems related to slums became more evident thanks to the debates post the 1956

act. By the early 1970s, the focus on health issues became diversified and other slum-related problems, including employment, education, infrastructure, and amenities like water supply and waste management, were addressed. Thereby, problematization of the initial project operationalized by the State, led to the questioning of its own episteme (what is being calculated). Concern for these issues started to problematize the previous emphasis on visibility (envisaging and presentation of slums), the lack of amenities, and the illegality of slums. This changing problematization of slums also cast doubt on the project of slum relocations, as a parliamentarian pointed:

Krishan Kant [INC]: ... Sir, what you are actually doing is you are removing them from one slum and putting them in another where the conditions are very clumsy and insanitary and they are away from their places of work. (Kant, 1970, p. 2)

To a similar probing, the minister replied:

H. K. L. Bhagat [Minister of State in The Ministry of Works and Housing, INC]: (a) The constructions have been allowed in accordance with the approved layout plans, which again are in accordance with the Master Plan and the zoning regulations. It is not correct to say that the clusters of small houses have become slums. (Sinha, 1976, p. 23)

The government's evasion of such criticism by pointing to the planned nature of the resettlements became the norm. The fact that a resettlement was planned got uncritically equated with the neighbourhood being legitimate, desirable, and better. Town planning has become the main governance tool for dealing with slums in the late 1960s and early 1970s.

Further, planning became the intellectual technology to discursively produce slums, i.e., slum as outside of planning, which continues till date. For example, Ghertner (2014) discusses how illegal real-estate development got legitimized by claiming that it was planned while slums are penalized for similar or arguably lesser degree of illegality in contemporary Delhi.

Furthermore, the increased recognition of multiple slum-related problems shifted the discourse towards an acknowledgement that to solve the problem of slums, one requires better understanding (questioning the episteme). The government's standpoint moved from one of resolve (to remove and resettle slums) to one of uncertainty, leading to the adoption of 'pilot projects' (Panda, Mohta, & Antani, 1970, p. 5), which can be seen as a stopgap solution because the project of slum relocation seemed no more viable.

The high cost and ineffectiveness of slum relocations further encouraged the government to shift its focus towards providing basic amenities in slums, which changed the discourse on slum demolitions. For the first time, demolitions were interpreted as a government action that reduces housing stock. Slums were no longer seen as epidemic areas from where people need to be rescued, but as potentially improvable localities. It became therefore worthwhile and necessary to improve the substandard houses and amenities. This became the prevalent discourse in *Rajya Sabha*, however, please note that slum demolitions continue till date in India, even when policies stipulate otherwise.

From June 1975 until March 1977, India was under an emergency rule, during which, brutal slum demolitions took place, especially in Delhi resulting in roughly 100-fold increase in demolitions (Shah, 1978). After the emergency, there was substantial support in the *Rajya Sabha* to discard the slum demolition policy completely. Nonetheless, there was a continuity in the discourse of slums as housing stock a few years before, during and after the emergency period.

The discursive shift towards slums as improvable localities also led in 1972 to a slum improvement scheme, the Environmental Improvement of Urban Slums (EIUS). EIUS outlined a framework for the provision of basic amenities such as toilets, drinking water, roads, etc. Similar to the 1956 act, EIUS did not provide any definitive definition of slums. However, the material implications were very different. The notification of an area as a slum under the 1956 act implied the possibility of eviction for residents and a liability for the property owners to invest in improvements or pay for demolitions. While a neighbourhood delineated as a slum under the EIUS received grants from the Central Government for civic amenity improvements. Consequently, the definition and delimitation of slums were no longer questioned and contested. During the previous era, slum was made into a project which subsumed myriad concerns including lack of amenities. However, with the shift in discourse, made provision of amenities as the principal concern of the project. In this manner, the state was able to dislodge other issues like housing from the slum project. The debates in the *Rajya Sabha* became centred on the quality and adequacy of the

government provisions in the demarcated slum areas. Questions became focused on details of the scheme and its impact on the quality of life of the slum dwellers.

In 1982, the Central Government included slum redevelopment in its 20-point programme (TPP), a list of 20 issues to be prioritized. As slum improvement is officially a State Government subject, its inclusion in the TPP meant that a central ministry could define targets and goals, and then evaluate the implementation and impact of the State Government actions. The Central Government used the EIUS to implement the TPP regarding slum improvement and measured its success mainly in terms of the number of people getting access to basic amenities. This focus represents a major shift from the previous emphasis on slum demolitions.

For the provision of civic amenities, more comprehensive slum data was required. Nonetheless, there was no slum census. The debates shifted to a more general understanding of the urban situation. The government resorted to sample surveys, or reports by planning organizations, producing gross approximations, as the following reply excerpt suggests:

Sunder Singh Bhandari [Jana Sangh (JS)], L K Advani [JS], Ram Lakhani Prasad Gupta [JS]: ... (a) [What is] the state-wise number of slum dwellers during the last three years, year-wise; (b) the number of slum areas in the country which have no provision for public conveniences; ...

Bhishma Narain Singh [Minister of Works and Housing, INC]: Though no accurate figures are available, it has been estimated that about 20 percent of the urban population may be living in slums...Statistics in regard to slum areas without public conveniences are not available.

(Bhandari, Advani, & Gupta, 1980, p. 207)

There are three major discursive shifts in this era distinguishing it from the previous one. First, the slum is understood as a neighbourhood that houses people rather than as an infected area from where people need to be rescued. Therefore, issues related to amenities, such as sanitation, health, employment, and education, got embedded in the problematization of slums. Second, the complex phenomenon of the slum was discussed within a larger urban framework compared to the previous era. Questions of slum growth were related to city growth rather than to anecdotal references to the urban poor squatting on available land. Third, these two shifts demanded a more comprehensive understanding of urban growth and mechanisms for the State to investigate urban growth towards producing the knowable subject of slums.

CITIES AS ENGINES OF ECONOMIC GROWTH: FROM MID-1980s UNTIL LATE-1990s

The demand for a broader understanding of urban growth and development encouraged the Central Government to appoint a National Commission on Urbanization (NCU), which submitted its report in 1985. Outlining its focus, the minister recounts:

‘The Commission came up with specific suggestions on a broad range of policy interventions necessary to bring about more efficient urban settlement management which could generate rapid economic growth with equity and social justice’ (M Arunachalam [Minister of State in The Ministry of Urban Development, INC] cited in Agarwal, 1991, p. 214)

Prior to the NCU report, the situation of cities was seen as a liability and the policies were focused towards bringing the social good to the population. By contrast, the NCU report represented cities as engines of economic growth, whereby spending on cities was now understood as an investment for a higher economic growth trajectory of the country. This discourse was quickly adopted in the *Rajya Sabha* where economic aspects of government actions were highlighted. In 1986, answering the question regarding the slum situation, the minister stated:

Dalbir Singh [Minister of State in The Ministry of Urban Development, INC]: ... A comprehensive study has been undertaken on the dimension of investments in slum improvement and urban development programme and its efficacy and impact on the quality of life of slum dwellers.(Gowda, 1986, p. 184)

It is noteworthy that slum improvement funds were being referred to as 'investments' in the above quote and elsewhere, while earlier they were called either 'grant' or 'spending'. More generally, development and the economy became the crucial elements in the discussions. A similar debate was revived at a global scale by the early 2000s with the Millennium Development Goals (Goal 7, Target 11). Huchzermeyer (2014) has argued that how the alliance between World Bank, United Nations Environmental Programme, and UN-Habitat, resulting in the Cities Alliance, sought to make cities bankable and competitive. As a result, the slogan of 'cities without slums', which essentially entails converting the cities to bankable entities and removal of slums, was geared towards attracting foreign direct investment. However, the Indian economy was not open to foreign direct

investment until the early 1990s, therefore the discussion shows the state as the primary investor. In the previous two eras the project of slum was representative of urban issues, however, in this era, it started to represent the issue of economic growth albeit not of the slum itself, but of the urban 'outside' of it.

While the understanding of slums as a complex phenomenon in the urban milieu continued in this era, town planning, which earlier was considered a crucial solution, was de-centred. Instead, the complex urban issues, including the slums, were now to be dealt with by the larger policy framework, as the following excerpt illustrates:

Sheila Kaul [Minister of Urban Development, INC]: ... the haphazard growth of cities including growth of slums are dependent on a complex set of factors and not town planning aspects alone ... inadequate local financial resources to provide civic amenities and develop infrastructure networks in anticipation of future developments and imbalances in the location of employment-generating activities and in the access to economic and social opportunities. No generalization is therefore possible regarding the causal nexus between haphazard growth of cities and neglect of town planning or basic amenities. (Patel & Pachouri, 1994, p. 29)

NCU recommended the provision of amenities and affordable housing irrespective of the legality of land tenure in slums. This changed discourse of the urban, as a phenomenon to invest in, implied that interventions in cities were no longer based on or justified by a social model but by an economic one. The Central Government started focusing on larger policy frameworks. In 1988, for example, the first National Housing Policy was

introduced in the *Rajya Sabha*. However, the first housing policy was heavily critiqued due to its isolated focus on shelter (house making) (Kidwai, 1988). Nonetheless, this narrow scope of the first housing policy was revised and a second housing policy was introduced in 1994. The second housing policy took a broader approach, including wider issues such as land, finance, infrastructure, NGOs involvement, etc., under its purview. It was again revised and replaced by the third national housing policy in 1998 that took a further neoliberal turn and positioned the government as a facilitator of housing production rather than as a provider.

These national level policies brought back targeted funding from the Central Government towards slum redevelopment, with the introduction of the National Slum Development Programme (NSDP), launched in 1996. The NSDP envisaged funding from the Central Government for a wide range of social and physical infrastructure, as well as housing improvements. The NSDP was targeting only the notified slums², therefore, the contestation of ‘what a slum is’ did not resurface in *Rajya Sabha*. Instead, the questions shifted to programme efficacies. A key aspect of the efficacy-related questions was the need to understand the larger impact of the government programmes, the housing deficit, or reduction in slum population. The government was able to answer by giving, for example, the number of houses built under the NSDP, but was not able to gauge its impact as the total number of slums in the country was not known.

² Notified under the 1956 act or its derivative.

In this era, slum improvement became a means to achieve larger economic growth. Therefore, the questions inside parliament were mainly related to the economic context of the country. Furthermore, there was an increasing demand for a more data-driven understanding of the situation. Slums were now reduced to stress points of an investment curve.

RIGHTS-BASED DISCOURSE: FROM EARLY-2000s UNTIL 2014

The call for more slum data eventually led to its inclusion in the national census of 2001. The census took a set of broad definitions bringing a wide array of settlements to the fold of what was rendered as slums. In part motivated by the availability of census data, the provisions of the NSDP was extended to all kinds of slums and a new scheme called Valmiki-Ambedkar Awas Yojana (VAMBAY) was launched in 2001.

Further, the census data became a tool for the parliamentarians to question the performance of the government. It was for the first time that the magnitude of the issue could be visualized through 'reliable' statistics, and the effectiveness of government schemes could be assessed quantitatively by the parliamentarians (c.f., visibility in (Legg, 2006)). In this era, the discussion around slums took a further neoliberal turn, that is, it developed an excessive focus, compared to previous eras, on statistics and managerial efficacies (Brenner & Theodore, 2005).

As investments in cities were now realized to yield economic growth, the Central Government launched in 2005 the Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission (JNNURM), the largest urban funding scheme till date. The scheme also had a submission to provide Basic Services to Urban

Poor, which especially focused on slum improvement. Being the largest urban funding scheme (INR 50,000 Crores over 7 years) (Kundu, 2014), JNNURM became the focus of *Rajya Sabha* debates on slums. Furthermore, the scheme was designed as demand driven, i.e., the cities needed to demand funds for specific projects. A central government body scrutinized funding applications that needed to be channelled through the State Governments, which now designed (usually via external consultancy firms) the JNNURM projects. The Central Government's main responsibility became fund management, through which it could nonetheless indirectly influence outcomes. Thus, the debates in the *Rajya Sabha* shifted to operational issues of JNNURM, e.g., on how much money was allocated to each city, how much of it is being utilized, and how this process could be improved for better outcomes. Similarly, qualitative contestations on slums got sidelined and statistical data on slums took centre stage. Questions as below became common occurrence in the *Rajya Sabha*:

Murli Manohar Joshi [Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP)], Ram Jethmalani [BJP]: ... (a) whether it is a fact that the number of people living in slums have increased in the metro cities of the country specially in the cities having ten lakh population during last five years; (Joshi & Jethmalani, 2007, p. 124)

Rama Chandra Khuntia [INC]: ... (a) the number of houses for urban poor that have already been constructed, state-wise and year-wise; (b) the details thereof and coming five years target, state-wise and year-wise; [are presented below in the table](Khuntia, 2009, p. 106)

In the first era, the slum was a project which subsumed in it the various urban concerns, leading to problematization of associated social

concerns. However, the slum in this era became a means to economic development, leading to the problematization of associated economic concerns.

At the same time, the availability of statistical data made it possible for the government to reduce the complexity and ambiguity regarding slums. By the late 2000s, the Central Government had arrived at a structured reply to the ever-occurring questions about the causality of slum growth. The following points by the minister figure at least eight times across different debates as it is, during this era:

Details of factors of growth of slums

(i) Inappropriate system of urban planning ... (ii) Sky-rocketing land prices ... (iii) Increased urbanization leading to pressure on the available land ... (iv) Natural increase in the population of urban poor and migration ... (v) Absence of legal framework/policy for security of land tenure and provision of land and housing ... (vi) Absence of programmes of affordable housing to the urban poor ... (vii) Lack of adequate investment in infrastructure and basic amenities in informal settlements... (Kumari Selja [Minister of Housing and Urban Poverty Alleviation, INC] cited in Waghmare & Singh, 2009, p. 78)

Further, the extrapolation of census data by the Technical Group on Estimation of Urban Housing Shortage pinpointed the deficit in housing numbers. This extrapolation established 99% of the urban housing deficit in the low income or economically weaker sections, making it a concern in the parliament (Mohan, 2011). Other slum-related issues problematized before, for example, amenities, or the causes pointed in the quote above, were dwarfed by the alarming housing deficit numbers. This problematization of

the data changed the ethos of slum governance. The deficit was morphed into the motto of 'affordable housing for all' in the fourth national housing policy (Ministry of Housing & Urban Poverty Alleviation, 2007). This motto was put into action by the Rajiv Awas Yojana (RAY) in 2011, which was the largest Central Government funded schemes specifically targeting slums. Thus, the problematization of slums got reduced back to housing. It is not that issues of education, employment or even malnutrition were not being discussed, but these discussions took place beyond the spatial confinements of the slums. Consequently, the only concern left with the spatially marked idea of slum was housing.

RAY reintroduced the idea of property rights to slum dwellers and further made the tenure right a mandatory factor for using the funds, building on arguments championed by de Soto (2002), who came to India in 2010 for policy deliberations. The government believed that by garnering property rights to the slum dwellers, they will become part of the neoliberal capital market capable of socio-economic upliftment. RAY promised a 'slum-free India' within five years, declared by the president herself during the joint parliament session of 2009 (Patil, 2009). This claim to make India slum free in five years, made *Rajya Sabha* discuss the progress towards this goal; even though the five-year time-limit was later dropped.

Furthermore, RAY was designed similarly as JNNURM: The State Governments could demand funding for specific projects, thereby taking the responsibility off the Central Government. This led to an increase in questions related to statistics on RAY fund usage by various State

Governments. A typical answer post-2011 had more than five pages of tabulated data attached. Compared to the late 1990s there was at least a three-fold increase of tabulated data in replies. Data presentation became so frequent that the government even planned for a slum index that would help measure its performance. The *Rajya Sabha* discussed such an index in the early-2010s (Raut, 2013), yet it was not created until at least 2014. The debates were dominated by management driven questions and their statistics driven answers leading to shrinking of political space for ‘slums’. By contrast, the questions which contested or probed the idea of slums or that of the government policies dropped.

In this era, there was the same belief as in the first era (early-1950s until late-1960s) that slums can be eradicated from India’s cityscapes. In the first era, it was to happen through demolition and rebuilding, and in this era it was via a mix of various upgradation strategies. In the first era, this belief resulted in a highly politically contested notion of what is understood as a slum. By contrast, by the late 2000s and early 2010s, the slum was produced as a knowable subject through statistics. Therefore, even though the Central Government policies were right-based, the discourse of slums in the *Rajya Sabha* shifted to that of managerial efficacies. With (i) measuring of slums by numbers, and (ii) precise, pointed, and uncontested recitals of the causes of the growth of slums, the slum subject was rendered a technical issue.

CONCLUSION

Within the four identified eras outlined in this article, we see a gradual change in how the subject of the slum was rendered comprehensible to the

State. These intellectual technologies made it possible for the State to develop a policy framework on slums. The discourses discussed in the four eras are not stages, rather amorphous periods, devised for heuristic purposes. Although, the discourse shifts, as outlined in the paper, the previous understandings are rarely completely erased, pointing to the presence of multiple discursive regimes. In the early 1950s, the goals were to demolish the slums, rebuild them, and rehouse its inhabitants elsewhere. The demolition agenda was cast aside by the early 1970s and the thrust shifted to providing amenities along with the already existing housing development focus until the mid-1980s. By the mid-1990s, in addition to amenities, larger planning and housing issues came into view; by the late 2000s, this got complemented by a willingness to give property rights to slum dwellers. Looking at the slum discussions in the *Rajya Sabha* from this angle of action towards slums, they present themselves as a 'progressive move forward' in policy discussions: from demolishing slums to providing property rights to slum dwellers. However, this narrative varies when one looks into *how* slums were discussed and their shrinking political space over this course of time. In the early 1950s there was no definition of slums, but the planned government action required slum demarcation. Therefore, slum delineations became highly contested with various political positions in the legislature. By the early 1970s, it was realized that demolishing all slums was not feasible. Thus, the policy shifted towards providing amenities and there was less of a need to demarcate slums. The discussions moved to numbers that represent a lack of amenities in slums

and in other neighbourhoods, reflecting a general understanding of the links between slums and urbanization. By the mid-1980s, the need to develop an urban vision was reinforced and eventually met through the NCU. At the same time, the debate shifted towards considering cities, including slums, as investment avenues for larger economic growth. By the late 2000s, this new discourse resulted in the creation of various funding schemes and a demand-driven policy framework. In parallel, the discussion shifted to statistical debates on managerial efficacies. Thus, we see the gradual transformation of the socio-political subject of the slum into a technical object that can be dealt with technocratically.

The dangers of using slums to drive anti-poverty policies of a government have been discussed by various authors (Gilbert, 2007; Huchzermeyer, 2011; Jones, 2011). However, slums need to be understood as a category produced by the State so that it becomes able to intervene. Therefore, the focus of the State will always be dependent on these categories and the discursive construction of slums themselves. Any action against the perpetual failing and disenfranchising slum policies will not yield any long-term results unless a comprehensive strategy is devised to understand and counter the discourses that produce them. To impact the lives of people living in so-called slums, in India and elsewhere, an effective step would also be, to challenge the categories of the State and its hegemonic knowledge production mechanism. This article is a modest step towards this, however, there is a further need to understand the production of slums through discursive practices, its link to urban poverty, and its

effects on initiatives to eradicate or uplift slums, in and beyond the legislative and executive domains of the State.

The analysis of this article ends in 2014, when a new right-wing government took power in India. One of the main urban missions of the current government is to create ‘smart cities’, mainly developing technology-driven solutions to urban issues, supported by even intensified data production and management. Furthermore, RAY has been replaced by Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana, with a neoliberal focus on using land as a resource. An analysis of the period from 2014 to 2019 will be stimulating to see how the urban has further been transformed into a technical, financial, and even digitalized, object.

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